

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Rabbit

Level: Slaughter

Keywords: Alternatively, stunning

Background context provided by the requestor

A slaughterhouse which is having problems with rabbits regaining consciousness wants to systematically stun twice. Is this a good solution?

Question raised by the requestor

A slaughterhouse which is having problems with rabbits regaining consciousness wants to add a second automatic stunner. The stun-to-bleeding interval is now 35 to 40 seconds. By making some changes to the infrastructure they could shorten this to around 20 seconds. Because this is still long, they want to add a second automatic stunner right before bleeding. They would still use the first manual stunner for hanging the rabbits on the line and then after about 20 seconds the rabbits would be automatically stunned again before being bled. So, all rabbits would be stunned twice. Is this a good solution?

Answer

INTRODUCTION:

[Regulation \(EC\) No 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing](#) (European Union, 2009) regulates the protection of rabbits at the time of slaughter in the European Union. According to this regulation, stunning methods must be effective in inducing unconsciousness without causing avoidable pain, distress, or suffering. This requirement is met when the method causes immediate unconsciousness that lasts until the death.

The regulation also mandates regular monitoring to verify the effectiveness of stunning. If checks reveal that an animal has not been stunned or regains consciousness, operators are required to take prompt corrective actions in line with their standard operating procedures.

STUN-TO-STICK INTERVAL:

[Anil et al. \(2000\)](#) demonstrated that the time to return of spontaneous breathing in head-only electrically stunned rabbits was approximately 22 seconds and an EU-wide survey of best practices in rabbit slaughterhouses indicated that maximum stun-to-stick interval is 10 s, exceptionally 20 s in one slaughterhouse ([European Commission, 2017](#)). According to [EFSA \(2020\)](#) the design and layout of slaughter facilities should be modified to keep the stun-to-stick interval to less than 10 s.

Supporting this, [Contreras et al. \(2025\)](#) demonstrated that in European commercial slaughter conditions, several factors significantly affect the depth and duration of unconsciousness, including head wetting, electrical parameters, and the stun-to-stick interval. Among these, maintaining a **stun-to-stick interval of less than 5 seconds** is critical to prevent animals from regaining consciousness before death, in commercial conditions.

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In this context, the currently practiced **35–40 second stun-to-stick interval** in the slaughterhouse mentioned by the requestor poses a high risk of rabbits regaining consciousness before or during bleeding. Even the proposed **reduction to 20 seconds** still carries a significant risk of animals recovering consciousness before death.

DOUBLE STUNNING:

While a second stunning may prolong unconsciousness (if effective), it does not address the root cause of ineffective stunning and/or the recovery of consciousness, which was the main issue identified in the slaughterhouse under review.

In accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009, **immediate corrective action** must be undertaken for the rabbits presenting indicator of consciousness and the systematic double stunning does not seem to address this point. There are two main reasons for that:

- The purpose of stunning rabbits is to prevent pain, distress, and suffering associated with being shackled while conscious and followed by neck cutting. Therefore, only those rabbits that were not properly stunned initially or that have regained consciousness should receive a backup stun. If rabbits are conscious while hanging on the slaughter line, they are likely to experience fear and/or pain. Allowing some animals to regain consciousness before applying a second stun does not prevent this from occurring.
- Additionally, the second stunning method itself would need to guarantee that all rabbits are fully stunned with it and ideally within 5 seconds before bleeding.

Moreover, based on the limited information provided by the requestor, it appears that the second stunner will consist of an **electrified plate or grid** through which shackled rabbits will pass, making contact with it using variable parts of the head. The automatic nature of this process, combined with the absence of continuous monitoring, increases the risk of ineffective stunning. This may result in rabbits receiving painful electric shocks, failure to induce unconsciousness, or regaining consciousness prior to neck cutting or during bleeding.

According to the **Centre' experience** in a slaughterhouse equipped with two rabbit stunning systems similar to those described by the requestor, rabbits were observed exhibiting signs of consciousness, such as vocalizations, after the application of the second stun.

Conclusions

In conclusion, based on the information provided, the proposed **double stunning method** fails to address the underlying issue of rabbits remaining conscious after the first stun or regaining consciousness before death. Indeed, an automatic second stun does not prevent pre-stun shocks that might occur in the second stunner nor guarantee effective stunning until death occurs.

A short **stun-to-stick interval** is critical to preventing rabbits from recovering consciousness before death, and according to the scientific articles cited above, it should not exceed 5 seconds. Currently, neither the first nor the second stunner achieves a sufficiently short stun-to-stick interval.

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